

PLAN'EAT

Living Lab Toolbox

Deliverable D5.1: Toolbox to set and run a Living Lab

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DELIVERABLE PLAN'EAT – D5.1

Living Lab Toolbox

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R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	X
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	
DMP	Data management plan	
ETHICS	Deliverables related to ethics issues.	
SECURITY	Deliverables related to security issues	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	

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Executive summary

This toolbox is designed to support the PLAN'EAT Living Labs leaders in creating, developing, and maintaining their Living Labs (LL) in a sustainable matter. It defines a joint methodology for the use and purpose of a series of tools that cover the essential elements of setting up a Living Lab, including key aspects such as:

- gathering a group of relevant stakeholders;
- running the LL and interacting with stakeholders & with the other WPs;
- guaranteeing stakeholder engagement;
- co-creating, co-designing, and testing the solutions of the project.

The tools presented in this guide were introduced to and discussed with the LL leaders in the monthly Community of Practice Forums (led by ESSRG). This toolbox has been presented, discussed, and validated during a dedicated workshop, conducted in M6 (February 2023).

What is in this toolbox?

The PLAN'EAT Living Lab Toolbox is meant to be a hands-on document, imminently practical, and a reference document LL leaders can consult.

The toolbox will provide tools and key information, divided into six chapters:

(1) What is a Living Lab:

- Terminology: definition of key terms linked to Living Labs
- PLAN'EAT's Living Labs, Policy Lab, and their target groups

(2) What is the Living Lab approach of PLAN'EAT:

- PLAN'EAT's Living Lab three-layer steering model
- Different phases of the LL process (initiation, preparation, co-creative design, co-evaluation, and monitoring)
- The LL engagement ladder approach

(3) INITIATION – Setting the ground

- Project level: project goals, types of stakeholders to gather, ensuring the information flow
- LL organisational level: pre-identify specific objectives based on the project goals, identify stakeholders

(4) PREPARATION – Getting ready for activities

- Project level: list of practice abstracts for each SPG (survey-protocol-guideline), general value proposition of the project
- LL organisational level: define the value proposition of each stakeholder group, draft a participant information sheet and informed consent form, pre-define a decision-making process, define a conflict management strategy, plan the schedule of all activities, adjust and translate the SPGs, prepare a stakeholder engagement strategy
- LL activity level: Contact LL stakeholders to build the core group, select and prepare incentives, organise a kick-off meeting (not mandatory)

(5) CO-CREATIVE DESIGN – Innovate together:

- Project level: set of co-creation tools selected within the consortium
- LL organisational level: preparation of the co-creative design activities
- LL activity level: selection and applying the tools during LL activities

(6) COMMUNICATION – Spread the message:

- Project level: general project communication strategy (see D6.1) and support to LLs
- LL organisational level: LL communication strategy
- LL activity level: Recommendations the LL's regular communication

(7) Conclusion and next steps:

- Guides the work continuation and provides the flexibility required to address any possible specificity of each LL

1. What is a Living Lab?

1.1 Terminology

LIVING LAB (LL)

As described by the European Network of Living Labs (ENOLL)¹, **Living Labs** are “real-life test and experimentation environments that foster co-creation and open innovation” through participatory, transdisciplinary, and systemic research among main actors of the stakeholder groups. Each LL should act as a key hub for knowledge production, exchange, and co-creation of tailored solutions with researchers from multidisciplinary expertise.

POLICY LAB

The **EU Policy Lab** is a collaborative platform to support macro-level activities and to act as an interface to gather expert and policy insights. Its main goals include (1) identifying policy trends and supporting the development of an integrated food systems agenda at the European level and (2) acting as an interface between policymakers and local food systems actors, fostering dialogue and collaboration between these groups. The Policy Lab brings together around 20 European policy makers and experts on food systems, nutrition, and sustainability, such as from the European Commission, the European Parliament as well as representatives from civil societies and the food industry.

*The **Policy Lab** does not always follow a similar approach to the LLs. If the differences are notable, a box like this will appear, marked with the EU flag.*

STAKEHOLDER

A **stakeholder** is an actor who is affected by the vision of the project, or should have the possibility to influence it, or should be involved in the process of realising the project². Their work has a direct impact on the outcome of the Living Lab. To better capture the different stakeholders and their role in the project, they have been divided by stakeholder groups.

STAKEHOLDER GROUPS

Stakeholder groups relate to a group of stakeholders as defined above. PLAN'EAT defined the following relevant **stakeholder groups** and their *sub-stakeholder groups* who will be gathered in LLs, depending on each LL target population group and level of action (local, regional, national):

- **Policy makers:** *local policy makers (e.g., from a city council); regional policy makers; national policy makers; European policy makers (Policy Lab only)*
- **Food value chain actors:** *farmers; food industries; retailers & supermarkets; food services & restaurants*
- **Educational systems:** *kindergartens, schools (primary- / -secondary); universities; national agencies of education*
- **Healthcare professionals:** *nutritionists/dieticians; nurses; doctors (paediatricians, general practitioners, endocrinologists, gastroenterologists, cardiovascular specialists, psychologists, etc.)*

¹ European Network of Living Labs. (n.d.). About us. Retrieved February 24, 2023, from <https://enoll.org/about-us/>

² Landau, P. (2022). What Is a Stakeholder? Definitions, Types & Examples. ProjectManager.com. <https://www.projectmanager.com/blog/what-is-a-stakeholder>

- **Local researchers:** *researchers in social sciences, policy science, economy of food systems, life cycle assessment of food products, agricultural science, food science, nutrition and health science.*
- **Civil society:** *civil society representatives; citizen panel members; non-governmental organizations (NGOs, in the Policy Lab only); civil society organisation (CSO, in the Policy Lab only)*

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

Stakeholder engagement refers to the process of identifying, analysing, and consciously interacting with internal and external stakeholders. From a social science perspective, stakeholder engagement is a process in which diverse stakeholders use a common forum, learn about each other's values, reflect on their own values, and develop a shared vision and objectives that align with the project goals³. Ethical dimensions, such as potential conflict of interests, equitable representation, and transparency in decision-making must be addressed before and throughout the process.

CITIZEN PANEL / CITIZENS

The **citizen panel** is a group of people who belong to the defined target group of the respective Living Lab. They will answer the surveys developed in the *surveys, protocols, or guidelines* (SPGs, 100 – 200 people). The group may change over the next 4 years; however, they must belong to the defined target group of each LL and have the same socio-demographic and -economic characteristics (gender, age, education, socio-economic status, nationality, health status).

Citizen panels are key players in PLAN'EAT, since their participation in the Living Labs is crucial for a better understanding and mapping of dietary patterns within a specific targeted group. Moreover, representatives of the citizen panel can and should be included in the Living Lab core group.

The **Policy Lab** will not include a citizen panel.

LIVING LAB CORE GROUP

The **Living Lab core group** includes all stakeholders that show a high interest in the project and actively participate in co-creation activities that the Living Lab may voluntarily set up, alongside the project activities. The purpose of the core group is to get the input and perspective of the different stakeholders on the project outputs. LLs are recommended to actively involve this group at least once a year to update them on the project development and to discuss and give feedback on the future direction of the project outcomes. The involvement of the LL core group is determined when planning the individual activities and depends on the objectives, budget, and the required prior knowledge of the participants.

Example: *The food policy recommendations are developed together with the policy maker stakeholder group. The involvement of the LL core group, and, thus, of bringing in the perspective of the other stakeholder and citizen, can be considered in two different ways:*

1. *The LL core group (or a part of its members) is invited to the policy summit, or*
2. *The results are shared with the core group and the LL may hold a (virtual) meeting with the core group to inform and discuss their thoughts in their (local) context.*

This core group may also include motivated citizens as representatives of the citizen panel. It will involve 10-20 actors and is open to change and development during the co-creation process of each LL. It can grow over the next three and a half project years and beyond. It is not essential that all stakeholder groups are equally involved from the beginning. For example, the activities planned with policy makers (e.g., the food system

³ Mathur, V. N., Price, A. D. F., & Austin, S. (2008). Conceptualizing stakeholder engagement in the context of sustainability and its assessment. *Construction Management and Economics*, 26(6), 601–609. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01446190802061233>

policy summits) will start later in the project (July 2024). To maintain engagement and interest and avoid pauses between activities, it may be useful to include stakeholders in the core group when their input is needed, rather than from the very beginning. However, the final core group must involve all stakeholder groups and should aim an almost even distribution of the different stakeholder groups.

1.2 PLAN'EAT's Living Labs, Policy Lab, and their target groups

PLAN'EAT has built nine Living Labs and one Policy Lab.

The Living Labs are spread across different European countries (Sweden, Poland, France, Germany, Ireland, Hungary, Italy, Spain and Greece).

The adjacent figure represents their geographical distribution and the research partners who act as Living Lab leaders.

The Living Labs will target pre-selected population groups that are presented below in Table 1 and Figure 2.

The **Policy Lab** is located in Brussels and will address policy makers and relevant actors within the policy process.

Figure 1: Living Lab countries and areas (own figure designed by SPXA and EQY)

TARGET POPULATION GROUPS

Figure 2: LL Target population groups in the Living Labs (own figure designed by EQY and SPXA)

Table 1: Target groups & context of PLAN'EAT's Living Labs and Policy Lab

SES= socio-economic status, NCDs = non-communicable diseases

Living Lab (LL)	Leader	Target population group (Age)	SES	NCDs	Setting	Participating Institutions/members
LL Sweden	SLU	Toddlers (Age: <6) and their parents	Middle/ High	No	COUNTRY (Sweden)	Food industry, Municipality, National policy representative, NGO, Nutritionist, University, School, Research institute, Supermarket
LL Krakow (Poland)	JU	Children and adolescents (Age: 1-16)	Low	No	DISTRICT (Nowa Huta district of Krakow)	Primary & Secondary School, University, NGO, Food service, Local policy representative, Nurse, Researcher
LL Auvergne (France)	INRAE	Children and adolescents (Age: 6-15), studying in rural and urban areas	Low/Middle/ High	No	REGION (Clermont-Ferrand Agglomeration and National Regional Park Livradois-Forez, peri-urban)	CSO, NGO, Farmer, Food industry, Food service, Restaurant, Local, Regional, & National policy representative, Waste management organisation, University, Supermarket, Primary and Secondary School, Research Institute, Media, Nutritionist, Nurse, Doctor
LL Bavaria (Germany)	TUM	Young adults attending University (Age: 18-30)	All	No	UNIVERSITY (TUM)	University, NGO, CSO, Clinic, Competence Centre, Food service, Restaurant
LL Dublin (Ireland)	UCD	Young adults attending University (Age: 18-30)	All	No	UNIVERSITY (UCD)	University, Health centre, Food service, Restaurant, Food industry, NGO, Supermarket

Living Lab (LL)	Leader	Target population group (Age)	SES	NCDs	Setting	Participating Institutions/members
LL Budapest (Hungary)	ESSRG	Healthy single parents, low SES (Age: 18 – 65)	Low	No	CITY (Budapest)	CSO, NGO, University, Farmer, Food industry, Food service, Restaurant, Local & National policy representative, Clinic, Nutritionist, Doctor, School, Supermarket, Research institute
LL Bologna (Italy)	UNIBO	Adults affected by type 2 diabetes and who belong to one of these ethnic groups: Italian, East European, North African, the Indian subcontinent (Age: 35-80)	Low	Yes	NEIGHBOURHOOD (Pilastro in Bologna)	Food Industry, Food service, Restaurant, University, NGO, Local & Regional policy representative
LL Catalonia (Spain)	UOC	Adults from work life to retirement and elderly (Age: 40-80)	All	No	REGION (Catalonia)	CSO, NGO, Food industry, Food service, Restaurant, Farmer, Supermarket, Regional Policy representative, University, Research Institute, Hospital, Nutritionist
LL Attica (Greece)	HUA	Elderly (not hospitalized or institutionalized) with certain risk factors for NCDs	All	Yes	REGION (Attica)	University, Health Centre, Food industry representative, Food service

Living Lab (LL)	Leader	Target population group (Age)	SES	NCDs	Setting	Participating Institutions/members
		(such as dyslipidaemia, hypertension, (pre)diabetes, obesity) (Age: >60)				
Policy Lab	Leader	Target group			Setting	
EU Policy Lab Brussels	EPHA	EU and national policy makers and other key European food policy stakeholders			CITY (Brussels)	Regional & National level policy representative, NGO, Food industry, Civil Society

2. What is the Living Lab approach of PLAN'EAT?

2.1 PLAN'EAT's Living Lab three-layer steering model

The following methodology is based on the material of the European Network of Living Labs ([ENoLL](#)) and their tailored coaching session for PLAN'EAT⁴. The three-layer model - originally created by Schuurman⁵ - was adapted to the specific needs of PLAN'EAT (see Figure 3).

At **project level**, the project partners who are responsible for the SPGs establish the general methodology for the activities carried out in LLs. The project level influences and *steers* the LLs by setting the general structure of activities, strategy, and outputs.

On the **LL organisational level**, the local network of each LL as well as the connection with (some) other LLs will be defined and established. During the project period, the LLs will form their local community (the Living Lab core group) and, if necessary, define additional (voluntary) activities to further engage the core group between project activities (e.g., organising a Kick-Off-Meeting, annual workshops, etc.).

At the **LL activity level**, all planned projects activities and (voluntary) additional LL activities are carried out. The local community and its meetings, communication channels, and other activities will continue beyond the PLAN'EAT project duration.

Figure 3: PLAN'EAT's three-layer steering model (own figure, designed by EPHA and SPXA)

2.2 Different phases of the LL process

PLAN'EAT will follow 5 phases as part of its LL process, based on the 'Living Lab way of working' proposed by Steen and Van Bueren (2017)⁶. These phases comprise: **initiation, preparation, co-creative design, co-evaluation, feedback and sustainability.**

⁴ Training and coaching session for the PLAN'EAT project – provided by the [European Network of Living Labs](#) (ENoLL) on 1 December 2022

⁵ Schuurman, D. (2015). *Bridging the gap between Open and User Innovation?: exploring the value of Living Labs as a means to structure user contribution and manage distributed innovation*. Ghent University. Faculty of Political and Social Sciences; Vrije Universiteit Brussel. Faculty of Economic and Social Sciences, Ghent; Brussels, Belgium

⁶ Steen, K., & van Bueren, E. (2017). *Urban Living Labs: A Living Lab Way of Working*. In D. Neutens & G. Schuurman (Eds.), *Proceedings of the ISPIM Innovation Summit* (pp. 1-13). *The International Society for Professional Innovation Management (ISPIM)*. Available from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318109901_Urban_Living_Labs_A_Living_Lab_Way_of_Working

This toolbox (D5.1) focuses on the first three phases of the LL process, i.e., phases one to three (initiation, preparation, and co-creative design) and on communication with practical recommendations and tools. The next deliverable on Living Labs (D5.2 – August 2026) will focus more on evaluation/feedback and sustainability.

2.3 LL engagement ladder approach

The **engagement ladder approach**⁷ is used to classify engagement tools and methods, according to the type of involvement and engagement level that these tools and methods have the potential to reach. The engagement ladder consists of 5 levels: inform, consult, involve, collaborate, and empower (see Figure 4).

Stakeholder engagement can take place using tools where stakeholders are **consulted, involved, invited to collaborate, or empowered**. **Co-creation** takes place when tools are used that enable **collaboration or empowerment** of stakeholder communities. The figure below includes some examples of objectives associated to the different levels of the engagement ladder:

Figure 4: Engagement ladder levels and respective examples of objectives (own figure, designed by ICONS and SPXA)

3. INITIATION – Setting the ground

3.1 Project level

PROJECT OVERALL GOALS

PLAN'EAT's overall goals are to:

1. Better understand and measure macro, meso, and micro factors influencing dietary behaviour in the EU.
2. Co-develop and evaluate macro, meso, and micro interventions to foster behavioural change.
3. Involve and engage up to 600 food system actors and 1800 citizens, for the project duration and beyond.

Additional information on the website: <https://planeat-project.eu/about/>

⁷ Arnstein, S. R. (2019). A Ladder of Citizen Participation. In Journal of the American Planning Association (Vol. 85, Issue 1, pp. 24–34). Informa UK Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944363.2018.1559388>

STAKEHOLDER TYPES TO GATHER

Each Living Lab should include representatives from the local food system – Farm to Fork -, policy makers, researchers, target population, healthcare professionals and educational systems (more details in Terminology-Stakeholder Groups).

The *Policy Lab* focuses on actors involved at macro- and meso-level, coming from (1) governance & public sector, (2) industry & business, (3) civil society, (4) advocacy organisations, and (5) think tanks.

Figure 5: Living Lab Composition (own figure, designed by SPXA)

PROJECT ORGANISATION AND INFORMATION FLOW

Two meeting types were agreed on and set at the beginning of the project:

- **WP5⁸ meetings** that include all WP5 partners⁹ and LL leaders for information exchange, e.g., what activities are next, which steps the LL must follow, and important information from the other WPs. It takes place every six weeks and is led by EPHA.
- **Community of Practice Forums (CoP)** provide additional support for all LL leaders by WP5 partners, SPG leaders and by co-creating a space for peer learning. The LL leaders can use it for exchange with the other labs, to connect, and to exchange questions, lessons learnt and best practices. It is also a place where the tools that are presented in this toolbox were and will be introduced. It takes place monthly and is led by ESSRG.

3.2 LL organisational level

PRE-IDENTIFICATION OF SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES AND VISION

Each Living Lab leader should start with a comprehensive analysis of their local context and of the situation of their target groups to become fully aware of the challenges, needs, and opportunities of their LL. As a result, specific objectives per LL should be identified, in line with the overall goals of PLAN'EAT. Each LL leader should clearly understand the needs and goals of their LL, be aware of the lens they have chosen, and define perspective and guiding principles. An initial vision and mission that goes beyond the project period, can also be defined at this stage by each LL leader before being further discussed with stakeholders at the **LL activity level** (e.g., at a kick-off meeting).

IDENTIFICATION OF STAKEHOLDERS

STAKEHOLDER MAPPING

The first step is to brainstorm and identify all the local actors who are stakeholders of the project (see definition above). During this process LL leaders need to consider the main project goals, their target group, as well as the specific objectives of their LL.

⁸ WP5 (Work Package 5) is the work package in the project that creates, implements, and consults PLAN'EAT's LLs.

⁹ The WP5 partners are ICONS, EQY, SPXA, CREA, ESSRG, and all LLs, led by EPHA.

Tools ¹⁰ (description and visuals)		Tested and approved by our LLs																
<p>Online platforms (e.g., Miro, Mural) or digital tools (e.g., Excel) can be used to map stakeholders. These visual tools help to think and work effectively either individually or in a group.</p>	<p>Source: https://miro.com/app/board/uxjvPPbon1A=/</p>																	
<p>The stakeholder mapping spreadsheet facilitates the listing of LL stakeholders, their interests, impacts and influence, and their contribution or issues.</p>	<p>Stakeholder Mapping Spreadsheet</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Stakeholder type</th> <th>Contact</th> <th>Topics of interest</th> <th>Impact level</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td> </td> <td> </td> <td> </td> <td> </td> </tr> <tr> <td> </td> <td> </td> <td> </td> <td> </td> </tr> <tr> <td> </td> <td> </td> <td> </td> <td> </td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Similar templates: https://templatelab.com/stakeholder-map/#Stakeholder_Maps</p>	Stakeholder type	Contact	Topics of interest	Impact level													
Stakeholder type	Contact	Topics of interest	Impact level															

STAKEHOLDER ANALYSIS

After mapping the relevant stakeholder, LL teams can carry out a more detailed **stakeholder analysis** involves gathering information about stakeholders, to understand their potential behaviour and interests in the project. This will inform the production of an effective communication and engagement strategy.

Tools ⁸ (description and visual)		Tested and approved by our LLs:
<p>The salience model helps to classify LL stakeholders based on their power (authority), legitimacy (involvement) and urgency (needs, priorities). The three main circles overlap, resulting in the sub-groups Core, Dangerous, Dominant and Dependent. These regions can serve as guiding principles to understand the position in the network and the level of attention each stakeholder needs.</p>		

¹⁰ Miller, P. (n.d.). Engage Stakeholders. pmillustrated.com. <https://www.pmillustrated.com/2-4-engage-stakeholders/>

In a **power and interest** matrix each stakeholder can be categorised by their level of *power* and *interest* in the project (low/high). They should be *engaged with* depending on their location in the matrix.

STAKEHOLDER REPORTING TEMPLATE

Going through the process of stakeholder mapping and analyses can support LLs in identifying the most relevant stakeholders to include in their core group. The LLs collect and report the stakeholders they will involve in the project in the **stakeholder reporting template**. A first list of about 10-20 stakeholders was collected by each LL by M6 (February 2023).

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	PART A: BASIC STAKEHOLDER INFORMATION							
2	Number	Name	Organization name	Type of organization	Stakeholder Group	Sub Stakeholder Group	Gender	Stage of Involvement
3	1							
4	2							
5	3							
6	4							
7	5							

4. PREPARATION – Getting ready for activities

4.1 Project level

LIST OF PRACTICE ABSTRACTS PER SPG

To support LL leaders in the preparation and implementation of project activities, practical abstracts per targeted stakeholder group were co-designed by EQY and SPG leaders for each SPG.

A reference document containing all these abstracts provides a more detailed overview of all project activities that need to be carried out in LLs in interaction with Work Packages (WP): **WP1** - Snapshot of European dietary patterns and food environments, **WP2** - Understanding factors and drivers influencing dietary behaviours, **WP3** - Understanding the environmental, social and health impacts of dietary choices, and **WP4** - Development of effective tools and strategies. These abstracts contain both internal information for the consortium (**colour code green** in the example below) and information that can be shared with the target actor during recruitment (colour code blue).

An example of a practical abstracts is presented below:

Target	LL CORE GROUP (all LL stakeholders except citizens)		
Activity	Survey on needs and current initiatives		
When?	May 2023 (M9)	Partner in charge	CREA
Short description	Share a survey to LL stakeholders (local food value chain actors, policy makers, healthcare professionals, researchers, educational systems) to assess the needs and current national and local initiatives implemented (T1.1.4 – SPG2) to foster dietary behaviour change and to improve food environments.		

<p>Purpose/ Goal</p>	<p>The goal of this survey is to understand your needs and the possible initiatives that you are adopting or that are adopted - at national and local level - to encourage changes in dietary behaviour and to improve food environments.</p> <p>The survey consists of multiple-choice questions together with an open question and in particular it will investigate your:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • needs to achieve a food system transition towards healthier and more sustainable diets, • expectations, requirements and needs regarding PLAN'EAT outcomes, • initiatives implemented – by you or in your area - that have reached positive outcomes to shift to sustainable and healthy food environments/food systems. <p>To complete the questionnaire, you will need 15-30 minutes (depending on your answer on the open question).</p> <p>The feedback obtained will feed into our European mapping and snapshot of food systems needs and initiatives, and will represent a basis for the development of tailored interventions.</p>
<p>Timeline</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feb-March 2023: First wave - survey ready, reviewed by CWG (Consultation and Working Group) leaders and sent to existing CWG members. • End of March 2023: Second wave - survey ready and sent to LL leaders for review. • May 2023: completion of the questionnaire from LL stakeholders (one month to send it back completed).
<p>Links to more information</p>	<p>Available on SharePoint (internal secured shared repository for PLAN'EAT partners) from March.</p>

GANTT charts per type of targeted stakeholder group were also created and included in the reference document. The timeline takes into account ethical approvals, translations and potentially avoidable periods (such as summer and Christmas holidays). An example for the target group **citizens** is presented below; the coloured lines represent the period in which citizens will be engaged in activities.

The reference document, which contains the list of practical abstracts, will be updated and completed as the project progresses. It contains further details on the purpose, the steps, and the schedule of each activity to be carried out in LLs.

WHAT DO STAKEHOLDERS GET FROM THIS PROJECT

The main value proposition linked to the participation to PLAN'EAT includes early access to:

- Up-to-date scientific knowledge on:
 - What is a healthy **and** sustainable diet?

- What is the real combined impact of food on health, the environment, economy, and society?
- What is a healthy **and** sustainable dietary behaviour? What and who influences it?
- How to change dietary behaviour?
- How to engage food systems actors in a transition to healthy and sustainable dietary behaviour?
- Concrete actions, recommendations, and tools to:
 - Address barriers to dietary behaviour and food systems transition;
 - Draft more integrated food system policies;
 - Implement or improve food education;
 - Reduce the health, environmental and socio-economic impacts of food;
 - Change behaviours of citizens and thus improve their health and well-being and reduce their environmental footprint.
- Access to the network:
 - Meet new local food system actors and expand the network;
 - Bridge the gap of communication paths between different stakeholder groups, not usually easily in contact;
 - Cooperate and identify synergies, from Farm to Fork and from citizens to policy makers.

PLAN'EAT addresses issues that echo the key principles and values of potential stakeholders. Thus, generating their intrinsic motivation is the most effective method to engage those stakeholders for the project duration and beyond, despite the lack of financial compensation. In addition, to maintain this motivation throughout the project, a set of incentives^{11,12,13} were defined and designed at **project level**, and will be adapted and/or prepared when planning the activities at the **LL activity level**. Together with the LLs, the following five most feasible incentives were identified:

- Healthy and sustainable food (e.g., fruits and vegetables basket during meetings, workshops)
- Voucher or a discount/gift card (e.g., for food from local businesses, museums, activities)
- Goodies (e.g., the PLAN'EAT bag, PLAN'EAT notebook, stickers)
- Free trainings/classes (e.g., partnership with the university, course credit, free courses, e-books)
- Field trips (e.g., in a farm)

As the project progresses, other possible incentives will be added and the list will be re-evaluated by gathering feedback from the LLs on what they used, what they found helpful and what left a good impression on the stakeholder group they used it for.

4.2 LL organisational level

DEFINITION OF TARGETED VALUE PROPOSITIONS, AS THE CORE INCENTIVE IS INTRINSIC MOTIVATION

Before involving the identified stakeholder groups in the project, it is essential to define the value proposition of the project and of the LL for each stakeholder. The main motivation for all stakeholders should be intrinsic and in line with their own professional and private goals and values. Based on the overall value proposition defined at project level, each LL leaders should apply one of the following tools to define a more tailored value for their LL and per stakeholder group.

¹¹ Gewertz, C., Nolan, M., & O'Brien, R. (2008). Using incentives to improve outcomes in out-of-school time programs. *Child Trends*. Retrieved from https://www.childtrends.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/05/child_trends-2008_06_18_pi_ostincentives.pdf

¹² Hester, Patrick & Baggett, K. & Shauger, Jennifer & Haynes, A.. (2010). Developing stakeholder incentives to encourage effective governance. 31st Annual National Conference of the American Society for Engineering Management 2010, ASEM 2010. 574-582. Retrieved from:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/289322390_Developing_stakeholder_incentives_to_encourage_effective_governance

¹³ Floyd, I., Research incentive programs – benefits, examples and instructions. Tremendous. Retrieved from <https://www.tremendous.com/blog/research-incentive-programs>, accessed in 21 November 2022

Tools (description and visuals)		Tested and approved by our LLs:																																																																					
<p>The stakeholder value importance matrix¹⁴ represents the values that the Living Labs brings to their stakeholders. After listing the values, the stakeholders can be categorized in the matrix to prioritize them accordingly.</p>																																																																							
<p>The stakeholder value table¹⁵ serves as a concise description of the benefits that the LL is expected to bring to the local population in the context of the project. It should serve as a declaration of intent, both inside the LL leading team and outside of the project, to the stakeholders.</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th rowspan="2">Stakeholder</th> <th colspan="5">Value proposition</th> <th rowspan="2">Importance level to the stakeholder</th> <th rowspan="2">Importance level to you</th> </tr> <tr> <th>Social</th> <th>Environmental</th> <th>Economic</th> <th>Functional</th> <th>Symbolic</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td></tr> </tbody> </table>	Stakeholder	Value proposition					Importance level to the stakeholder	Importance level to you	Social	Environmental	Economic	Functional	Symbolic																																																									
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DRAFTING OF A PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET AND INFORMED CONSENT FORM

For the first contact with the stakeholders and the citizen panel an information sheet and participant template were prepared for use and adjustment by each LL leader. LL leaders have to translate the draft in their local language and adapt it, if needed, for the different stakeholder groups and the citizens, so every citizen has fully understood what they are signing up for. It is especially critical that all participants have a clear understanding of the research’s purpose, as well as of the risks and benefits that this may imply.

Recommendation: remember data protection!

LL participants are ensured with a high level of data protection according to the European legislation (the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 - known as GDPR). The compliance with the GDPR, and therefore with the participants data rights, must be ensured through all their engagement. This includes, for example, that **personal data** (i.e., names and last names, e-mail addresses, age, profession, and health status) **cannot be shared to others without the previous written consent of the participants**. Same for taking pictures, and recording the conversation for further analysis.

Furthermore, the collected data can only be used for the purpose of this project, and as long as the project lasts. This means participants cannot be contacted at any time for a reason different to the project.

The data should be stored in a secure location: If a folder is used in the computer, it must be ensured that only the responsible person has access to this folder (e.g. restricting access to the folder, setting a password).

Keep in mind that any participants are entitled at any time to withdraw their participation, and they can request for their data not to be shared with others.

¹⁴ Mitchell, R. K., Agle, B. R., & Wood, D. J. (1997). Toward a Theory of Stakeholder Identification and Salience: Defining the Principle of Who and What Really Counts. *The Academy of Management Review*, 22(4), 853–886. <https://doi.org/10.2307/259247>

¹⁵ Own table based on Valkama, V., & Ojala, T. (2011). Stakeholder value propositions on open community testbed of interactive public displays. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Management of Emergent Digital EcoSystems* (pp. 107-113). <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2077489.2077509>

For more information, the project's Data Management Plan, the colleagues from CREA, or the ethic advisor can be consulted.

PLAN'EAT – LIVING LAB

Participant Information Sheet

You are being invited to take part to a research project called PLAN'EAT. Before decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being conducted what it would involve for you. Please take time to read the following information care and to decide whether or not you wish to take part. Talk to others about the study if wish. Ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information

Thank you for reading this!

Study title

Specify a title according to the type of research you will be doing within your organisation

What is the purpose of the research project?

The purpose of the research project is to discuss about your eating behaviour and your health in order better understand factors of influence and means of actions towards healthier and sustainable diet patterns.

This research is part of an important project called PLAN'EAT "Food systems transformation towards healthy and sustainable dietary behaviour" funded by the European Union under the agreement number 101063

Participant Consent form

The purpose of the research is related to the objectives of the PLAN'EAT project.

With the signature I confirm that my participation is voluntary.

- I have been informed about the treatment of my data by the DPO of [name of the living lab] /the PLAN'EAT consortium and I authorise their use
- I hereby authorise the use of my personal image (e.g. pictures taken during workshops to be published on the project website or social media (optional)) in order to contribute to the implementation of the PLAN'EAT project activities
- Authorisation for the secondary use of data

Please read the following statement:

I have read the above description; I have had sufficient information to decide whether or not I wish to take part in the study. I understand that I am free to withdraw from the research at any time by informing the researcher of this decision. I understand that the information I give will be treated in the strictest confidence. I explicitly consent to take part in the project according to the data protection regulation (General Data Protection Regulation/GDPR)

I confirm that data obtained can be used during the development of PLAN'EAT project in order to achieve the above mentioned objectives. I understand that the data will be used anonymously and aggregated.

Full Name _____
e-mail _____
Date _____

Personal data will be treated in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679. Data exchange between the project partners via project intranet or encrypted document. Data will be stored in the project intranet during the project lifetime and 5 years after the end of the project. The information will be used only for the project purposes.

If you have any questions or wanted to exercise the right recognised in Chapter III of GDPR; including but not limited to: right to access, right to be forgotten or right to object, please contact XXX.

The Policy Lab will use a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU).

In order to facilitate effective collaboration and linkages as a commitment between the parties, a MoU will be created. The MoU is deemed to be a beneficial agreement that joins parties together in order to achieve a specific outcome, and will help to solidify partnership among the participants of the Policy Lab through a respectful collaboration mindful of participants' rights, and of the resolution of potential conflicts. The MoU will be created with the objective to provide a framework to rule the relations between the Policy Lab coordinator (EPHA) and the different stakeholders. It is non-binding and based on mutual understanding that will be setting ground rules for the organization, defining roles, participants' rights, responsibilities, data sharing, conflict resolution, management of conflict of interests, and distribution of tasks.

Within the initiation phase, a MoU will be prepared and will be tailored for the particular aspects of the Policy Lab, differing from those employed on the other LL.

PRE-DEFINITION OF A DECISION-MAKING PROCESS AND GOVERNANCE STRUCTURE

A first decision-making process and governance structure will be defined for each LL in terms of how and by whom decisions on the LL strategy, implementation of activities, and day-to-day decisions will be made. This

decision process will be discussed with or at least presented to LL stakeholders during the LL kick-off meeting (LL KOM) or – if a LL KOM is not possible - the information will be made available to all stakeholders.

CONFLICT MANAGEMENT

PREVENT POTENTIAL INNER PROJECT CONFLICTS

Adopting new ways of working is particularly hard when there is a tension between encouraging innovation and creativity and delivering tangible results quickly.

At **organisational level**, LL leaders will have to follow two potentially conflicting paths:

1. The objectives, specific deadlines and instructions set in the Work Plan, and
2. The creative approach at the **LL activity level**, which aims to create space for new ideas and approaches.

To address this tension, SPG leaders have been asked to provide and encourage as much flexibility for new ideas and contributions as possible, while clarity about the project objectives at the **LL activity level** frames the LL activities and prevents disappointment.

PREVENT POTENTIAL STAKEHOLDER CONFLICTS

Moreover, conflicts can arise among individual stakeholders and stakeholder groups due to their different interests and stakes that they bring to the LL. The LL leader can anticipate and avoid possible conflicts between stakeholders by understanding deeper which issues are important for each stakeholder or group and whether certain stakes might be shared or in opposition using the following tool:

Tools (description and visual)	Tested and approved by the LLs:
<p>The stakeholder-issue interrelationship diagram¹⁶ helps to understand the interests of the different stakeholders and how they relate to each other. By identifying these issues, the problems and areas of conflict or cooperation can be structured.</p>	

All LL leaders are strongly encouraged to be transparent about any potential conflict and to inform the WP5 lead (EPHA) as early as possible.

SCHEDULE

¹⁶ Bryson, J. M. (2004). What to do when Stakeholders matter. Public Management Review, 6(1), 21–53. [link: https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/14719030410001675722?casa_token=Vbq6fjce-4EAAAAA%3AhWnv0_r_zzbHKHAr7v0SG_PwiZyQfiY-PbwNEKo35FZNXDtFeZ1U3bTo7ArvJR5Sj78dSYlvopa7](https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/14719030410001675722?casa_token=Vbq6fjce-4EAAAAA%3AhWnv0_r_zzbHKHAr7v0SG_PwiZyQfiY-PbwNEKo35FZNXDtFeZ1U3bTo7ArvJR5Sj78dSYlvopa7)

Based on the timeline included in the list of practice abstracts, each LL leader needs to plan its timetable for LL activities, including time for ethical approvals, preparation, and adaptation of each SPG, translation, organisation of invitations and locations. LL leaders also need to take into account the schedule of their target group (e.g., school or semester holidays).

ADJUSTMENT AND TRANSLATION OF SPGS

Each LL leader must first thoroughly understand each SPG and participate in its design, notably by attending workshops organised by each SPG producer, asking questions, and providing feedback on the content. Then, they must adjust the SPGs to their local context and target group, with the help of local researchers or SPG producers, if needed, and translate it in their local language.

Recommendation: talk the language of the participant!

Different stakeholder groups speak differently. The use of expert jargon is efficient for communication between people from the same field (e.g., expert jargon in research field) whereas communication aimed at the whole LL core group, where diversity of participants and interaction are essential, can lead to the exclusion of non-experts. Therefore, it is important to keep language simple and try to eliminate jargon as much as possible to make all participants feel welcome, interested, and willing to engage, because this ultimately stimulates creativity and encourages the development of innovative ideas.

PREPARATION OF ACTIVITIES ACCORDING TO THE STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT LADDER

In line with the LL engagement ladder approach, each LL leader can plan the means by which they will engage with stakeholders according to their level of engagement. The two steps are:

(1) Identify the level of engagement of each stakeholder.

Tool (description and visuals)		Tested and approved by the LLs:																		
<p>The participation planning matrix¹⁷ serves as the basis for developing action plans for each stakeholder group to follow up with.</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th rowspan="2">Strategic Management Function or Activity:</th> <th colspan="5">Stakeholders to Approach by Which Means:</th> </tr> <tr> <th>Inform</th> <th>Consult</th> <th>Involve</th> <th>Collaborate</th> <th>Empower</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Promise: We will keep you informed.</td> <td>Promise: We will keep you informed, listen to you, and provide feedback on how your input influenced the decision.</td> <td>Promise: We will work with you to ensure your concerns are considered and reflected in the alternatives considered, and provide feedback on how your input influenced the decision.</td> <td>Promise: We will incorporate your advice and recommendations to the maximum extent possible.</td> <td>Promise: We will implement what you decide.</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Strategic Management Function or Activity:	Stakeholders to Approach by Which Means:					Inform	Consult	Involve	Collaborate	Empower	Promise: We will keep you informed.	Promise: We will keep you informed, listen to you, and provide feedback on how your input influenced the decision.	Promise: We will work with you to ensure your concerns are considered and reflected in the alternatives considered, and provide feedback on how your input influenced the decision.	Promise: We will incorporate your advice and recommendations to the maximum extent possible.	Promise: We will implement what you decide.			
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(2) Define action plans for each stakeholder group based on their engagement ladder.

After categorising their stakeholder according to the engagement ladder, each LL leader should define actions plans for each stakeholder group. The latter include which tools they will use with which stakeholder, based on their level of engagement, as well as any contact and engagement with the stakeholders throughout the project (e.g. communication).

To support LLs in identifying and selecting the most appropriate stakeholder engagement tools and methods, ICONS has developed a **STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT CANVAS TEMPLATE**.

This selection will depend on two main factors:

- 1) The type of stakeholders that are engaged.

¹⁷ Bryson, J. M. (2004). What to do when stakeholders matter: Stakeholder identification and analysis techniques. *Public Management Review*, 6(1), 21-53. doi:10.1080/1471903042000214509; Bryson, J. M. (1995). *Strategic planning for public and nonprofit organizations: A guide to strengthening and sustaining organizational achievement*. Jossey-Bass.

2) The purpose for the engagement of stakeholders.

When selecting engagement tools, special attention should be given to the cost, time, resources, and skills needed to adopt such tools and methods.

This is repeated for each co-creation activity carried out in the LL. The engagement tools are chosen according to the objectives of the LL, the level of engagement one wants to achieve, and according to the LL process phase the LLs are in.

Table 2: Stakeholder engagement canvas template

LL PROCESS PHASE (Insert)	<i>Please specify which project process phase the planned activity is in...</i> Understanding the phases (initiation, preparation, co-creative design) of the activity to identify which level of the engagement ladder the activity should target.				
STAKEHOLDER TYPE (Select)	Target population group (i.e., citizen panel)	Organisations, associations, institutional stakeholder type (i.e., policy makers, schools, food value chain actors)		All	
NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (Insert)	<i>Please specify...</i>				
ENGAGEMENT LADDER & OBJECTIVE (Select)	Inform	Consult	Involve	Collaborate	Empower
	- Present the project - Generate interest - Increase awareness	- Request feedback - Analyse acceptance	- Gather requirements - Identify needs - Validate solutions - Build consensus	- Generate ideas - Co-create and co-design solutions - Envision the future - Co-implement solutions	- Community decision making
	Ensure equitable representation; avoid/manage conflict of interest; foster transparency in decision-making.				
RESOURCES (Insert)	<i>Please specify any available resource (ICTs, budget etc.)...</i>				
LENGTH OF THE PROCESS (Insert)	<i>Please specify...</i> How long does the planned activity last (without preparation time)? There are methods that take only a few hours and others that take longer and require more than one session.				
FORMAT (Insert)	<i>Please specify...</i> Online? On-site?				
SKILLS (Insert)	<i>Please specify...</i> What skills are in-house that could be used to guide the engagement activities?				

4.3 LL activity level

CONSTRUCTION OF THE LL CORE GROUP

- First contact the key stakeholders the LL leader has analysed in the Initiation phase, who are most motivated by the project and with whom the LL leader is planning activities in the coming months/years (e.g., in the case of PLAN'EAT, policy makers can be contacted later).
- Contact the different stakeholders with an information sheet and informed consent form (or first with a concept note and application form).
- If needed, plan an introductory call to answer any question and verify intrinsic motivation.

Recommendation: let the Living Lab grow organically!

LL leaders should not compile the list of LL participants only according to the results of the stakeholder identification. Instead, the **selected participants should discuss whether further potential stakeholders should be brought in the process** if their stakes are considered relevant and complementary. This leads to an organically grown LL which increases the diversity of LL stakeholders, and helps build trust. However, the final core group must involve all stakeholder groups, should be of 20 actors maximum and should aim a nearly equal distribution of the different stakeholder groups.

All **Policy Lab** stakeholders can be interpreted as **the core group**.

However, the construction of the Policy Lab cannot be as flexible and open to stakeholder motivation as in the case of Living Labs, because the Policy Lab must ensure symmetrical and balanced participation to guarantee a fair contribution from all participants from the start.

Ensuring balanced participation is particularly relevant for NGOs and CSOs, who are often invited to events to “NGO-wash” the debates, this means to give the impression they do count on NGOs and take their opinions into account, when the reality might differ.

SELECTION AND PREPARATION OF THE MOST RELEVANT INCENTIVES FOR THE PLANNED ACTIVITIES

Based on the list of incentives defined in the **Preparation** phase at **project level**, each LL leader will prepare and organise incentives per type of stakeholder group and/or age group – while trying to keep expenditure to a minimum – to boost the motivation of the stakeholders and target population groups and thank them for their participation.

ORGANISATION OF A LL KICK-OFF MEETING (LL KOM)

It is strongly recommended to organise an in-person LL Kick-Off-Meeting (LL KOM) in the first year of the project with stakeholders from the core group already gathered, to:

- provide communication materials, incentives and goodies to welcome participants in the LL;
- present and agree on the LL governance and decision-making process; and
- discuss of and agree on:
 - a more precise vision and detailed mission for the Living Lab,
 - the future proceeding around the activities that are planned by the project,
 - the frequency of future meetings/workshops (voluntary).

In the case of PLAN'EAT, a LL KOM is not mandatory because it was not originally budgeted. If the LL cannot hold a KOM, these steps should be taken during the first activities.

Recommendations:

1/ Openly communicate all aspects of the LLs decision-making!

- As a LL is most often a parallel process to the *official* decision-making process, the initiator of the LL needs **to be transparent about the goals of the LL, including to a main extent PLAN'EAT's project goals** and its position within the (formal) policy process. It must be clear from the beginning that the results, solutions, and plans developed within the LL **might or might not** be taken up in the decision-making process, therefore eliminating potential frustrations as well as managing expectations.
- It is important to clearly distinguish the creative process from formal decision-making and to constantly review possible expectations on the outcome. To emphasise this separation, it is important that LL decision-makers provide feedback throughout the project about their decisions and how they were arrived at.
- Not all aspects discussed within a LL activity can be communicated to the larger group. Therefore, agreements about the confidentiality of specific aspects need to be explicitly agreed on with the representatives at the start of the process. This is to prevent potential tensions and conflicts that may lead to mistrust and spoil the creative mindset. If needed, these agreements can be added to the participants consent form and signed at the first activity by all participants.

2/ Include the LL participants in decisions about the process!

- Participation in the LL is on a voluntary basis. Therefore, it is not only the 'product' of the LL that is co-created, but also the process. This includes discussions about the frequency and topics of the meetings as well as plans and ideas beyond the project horizon to ensure the existence of the Living Lab beyond the project.

The following list contains a suggestion of tools (related to the engagement ladders *Inform*, *Consult*, and *Involve*) that can be used for the LL KOM and other meetings/workshops (voluntary).

| INVOLVE |
|---|---|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meeting • Information repositories • Fact sheets, newsletters, and bulletin | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion forum • Survey • Focus groups • Feedback kiosks | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Area forum • Conversation Café • Distributed dialogue • Fishbowl conversations |

5. CO-CREATIVE DESIGN – Innovate together

5.1 Project level

SELECTION OF POSSIBLE TOOLS FOR EACH PROJECT CO-CREATION ACTIVITY

Based on ICONS's catalogue, SPG leaders have pre-selected four co-creation tools as the most appropriate to use in the co-creation activities of their SPGs. The four shortlisted tools were then sent to LL leaders to have their feedback on feasibility and their validation.

ICONS designed the following overview cards for each co-creation tool^{18,19,20,21,22}.

¹⁸ Facilitate Consensus Workshop (2021) *Facilitate consensus workshop*. Top Network. <https://www.top-network.org/facilitate-consensus-workshop>.

¹⁹ Consensus Workshop (2019) *Consensus Workshop Overview*. The Institute of Cultural Affairs – ICA. <https://ica-uk.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Consensus-Workshop-Overview.pdf>

²⁰ Welcome to the toolbox of the GreenSAM Project! (2021) *Welcome to the Toolbox of the GreenSAM project!*. GreenSAM Project. Interrect Baltic Sea Region. <https://greensam.eu/toolbox/>

²¹ Aakerblom K. and Ness O. (2021) Peer support workers in co-production and co-creation in public mental health and addiction services: Protocol for a scoping review. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0248558>

²² Arnstein SR (2019) *A ladder of citizen participation*. Journal of the American Planning Association (85) 1. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944363.2018.1559388>

Tool cards of engagement ladder *collaborate*

Objective: Generate ideas; co-create and co-design solutions; envision the future; co-implement solutions

Tool name: Consensus workshop	Description	A consensus workshop is a type of workshop that allows different stakeholders to work together. This type of workshop is a five-stage process that enables a facilitator to draw out and weave together everybody's wisdom into a clear and practical consensus, to find common ground and deliver consensus-based input. The workshop is a dialogue between experts and non-experts. This is an opportunity to include all stakeholders, especially marginalized communities.			
	Why use it?	- Open and transparent process - Can generate consensus on a specific issue - Low costs	Format	Online/Onsite	
	Issues	- A good facilitator is needed - Can be time consuming	Num. of participants		10-20
			Process		
			Length	2-4h	
		LL process phase	Co-creation		

Implementation Process

- | | | |
|--|---|---|
| 1. Context (Set the stage) (10 min)
1) State the purpose or aim of the workshop
2) Clarify the focus question
3) Briefly outline the process and time frame
4) Lead the group in talking about the topic | 3. Cluster (form new relationship) (20 min)
1) Have the group form 4-6 pairs that clearly go together
2) Ask for 2 nd round of cards, then develop clusters
3) Quickly give each cluster a symbol/tag
4) Mark remaining cards with symbol/tag and pass up | 5. Resolve (confirm the resolve) (15 min)
1) Focus the group on this consensus by reading all the cards
2) Discuss the significance of the consensus
3) Create a chart or visual to hold the consensus (optional)
4) Discuss implementation and next steps |
| 2. Brainstorm (Generate new ideas) (20min)
1) Individually list answers to the focus question
2) Select best ideas and write them on cards (I or T)
3) Pass up first round of cards. Ask for the clearest cards
4) Ask for questions of clarity | 4. Name (discern the consensus) (30min)
1) Talk through the largest cluster first
2) Give the cluster a 3-7 word name or title which answers the focus question
3) Repeat for the remaining clusters | |

Objective: Generate ideas; co-create and co-design solutions; envision the future; co-implement solutions

Tool name: Peer assist	Description	A participatory method of learning with and through peers by sharing experiences, insights, and knowledge. The method is designed to develop context-specific solutions to a challenge, based on participant's previous practices and experiences. Collaborative analysis is carried out to adapt action to a specific situation. The method enables exchange of tacit knowledge and good practices to assist a peer in a particular activity or challenge			
	Why use it?	- Engages stakeholders through cooperative dialogue - Supports the idea of self-help & needs-based, appreciative learning - Low costs	Format	Online/Onsite	
	Issues	- Assessing the quality of a peer-to-peer exercise might be difficult	Num. of participants		10-20
			Process		
			Length	2-4h	
		LL process phase	Co-creation		

Implementation Process

- 1) Communicate the purpose. Peer Assists work well when the purpose is clear, and you communicate that purpose to participants. Share your Peer Assist plans with others. Consider whether others have already solved the problem; they may have similar needs.
- 2) Identify a facilitator external to the team. The facilitator is responsible for managing the process so that meeting participants reach the desired outcome. Schedule a date for the Peer Assist. Ensure it is early enough to do something different with what you have learned.
- 3) Invite potential participants who have the diversity of skills, competencies and experience needed for the Peer Assist. Avoid the usual suspects. Peer Assist works well with six to eight people; break up larger groups so everyone has the opportunity to voice experiences and ideas.
- 4) Be clear on what you want out of the Peer Assist (usually options and insights) and plan the time to achieve them. Allow time to socialise to develop rapport.
- 5) Spend time creating the right environment for sharing. Plan the event to allow a balance between telling and listening.
- 6) Listen for understanding and for how you might improve your own activity.
- 7) Consider others who might benefit from this knowledge, then share it with them.
- 8) Commit to actions and keep the Peer Assist team updated.

Tool cards of engagement ladder *empower*

Objective: Community decision making							
Tool name: Stakeholder working group	Description	The method is designed as a workshop that enables focused discussions between different groups of stakeholders. The method consists of five steps (information, selecting topic, discussion, deliberation, and vote) of which some can be repeated if more than one research scenario is to be enriched by each group.					
	Why use it?	- Flexibility over length and frequency of sessions - Can offer a series of workshops that build on one another - It is a pure co-creation technique	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="background-color: #e0f2f1;">Format</td> <td>Online/Onsite</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="background-color: #e0f2f1;">Num. of participants</td> <td>10-20</td> </tr> </table>	Format	Online/Onsite	Num. of participants	10-20
	Format	Online/Onsite					
	Num. of participants	10-20					
Issues	- Can be time consuming - A skilled facilitator is needed - The cost may vary	Process					
		Length	Ongoing				
		LL process phase	Co-creation				
Implementation Process							
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Planning and preparation: Identifying key stakeholders, setting goals and objectives for the working group, and establishing ground rules and communication protocols. 2) Stakeholder engagement: The working group methodology should include mechanisms for engaging stakeholders throughout the process, including consultation, collaboration, and consensus-building. This may involve the use of tools such as surveys, interviews, focus groups and workshops. 3) Information gathering and analysis: stakeholders should have access to relevant information to enable informed decision-making. This may involve the collection and analysis of data, as well as the sharing of information and expertise among group members. 4) Decision-making: The stakeholder working group methodology should include a clear process for making decisions, including mechanisms for prioritizing issues and developing consensus among group members. 5) Implementation: Once decisions have been made, the working group should develop an implementation plan, including timelines, responsibilities, and monitoring and evaluation mechanisms. 6) Evaluation and feedback: The methodology should include mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of the working group, including the outcomes achieved, the process followed, and the satisfaction of stakeholders involved. 							
Objective: Community decision making							
Tool name: User committee	Description	This method involves users and other stakeholders in the formal monitoring and steering of the research and innovation process. The user committee co-design method is an effective way to ensure that the final solutions meet the needs of the end-users/target population. It also increases user engagement and satisfaction and can lead to a more successful solution.					
	Why use it?	- Changes can be tracked over time - Solutions focused - Can result in systemic change	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="background-color: #e0f2f1;">Format</td> <td>Online/Onsite</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="background-color: #e0f2f1;">Num. of participants</td> <td>10-20</td> </tr> </table>	Format	Online/Onsite	Num. of participants	10-20
	Format	Online/Onsite					
	Num. of participants	10-20					
Issues	- Time consuming and long-term commitment - Committee members are not necessarily representative - The committee will not deliver statistical information - A small number of people may dominate the group - The cost may vary	Process					
		Length	Ongoing				
		LL process phase	Co-creation				
Implementation Process							
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Identify the purpose and scope of the committee. 2) Define the user committee's role and responsibilities: Will they be involved in the design process from the beginning or only specific phases? What is expected of them? 3) Recruit user committee members and provide clear expectations of their role and responsibilities. 4) Facilitate communication and collaboration: regular meetings, online forums and so on. 5) Conduct user research to gather insights into the needs, preferences, and pain points of the end-users. Then, organize co-design sessions with the user committee to involve them in the design process. 6) Develop prototypes based on the co-design session and test them with the user committee. Gather feedback and make necessary revisions. 7) Develop the final solution based on the feedback from the user committee. 							

During the project implementation, the two steps should be followed for co-creation activities:

1. For each SPG, the SPG leaders select from these four tools about two tools that can be used in their SPG.
2. From that selection, LL leaders choose one tool to use when implementing the SPG.

If there is no agreement between the LL leader **at activity level** and the SPG leader at **project level**, the catalogue of engagement tools will be revised, and new tools may be proposed. If necessary, other co-creation tools and their cards are available in ICONS's catalogue (see the list below). ICONS has therefore compiled detailed information on the following tools in the engagement tools catalogue.

| EMPOWER |
|--|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Envisioning the future • Forum theatre • Six thinking hats | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenge Prize • Citizen Juries |

As the project progresses, the presented four tools will be re-evaluated by gathering feedback from the LLs on what they used, what worked best with the stakeholder group they used it for, and what other potential tools could be added.

5.2 LL organisational level

PLANNING A CO-CREATION ACTIVITY

When planning the LL activities, the following points should be considered:

- Which co-creation tool offered by the SPG leaders is best suited for the LL;
- Which and how many *individual* stakeholders should be involved for the activity, taking into account the guidance of the respective SPG leader;
- What support is needed from the **project level** (e.g., training, documents), and what support and synthesis can be built with other LLs (e.g., knowledge sharing or joint planning for LLs that have overlaps in their target group, as, for instance, school children);
- What expertise is needed and who in the organisation can do this activity (who has knowledge in working in this area, who is available when, who can be trained);

Recommendation: ask for support from the WP5 partners!

Especially if several exercises are carried out in succession during the LL activities, it is highly recommended that a coordinator takes on the role of facilitator. Facilitators can be trained in advance by ICONS if needed.

- Do the SPG objectives - set by SPG leaders - fit or do they need to be refined (not changed) to the LL's objectives? In consultation with the respective SPG leader, the LLs may set a target group or local focus, if needed;
- Which location can be used for the activities?

Recommendation: use a neutral location!

A neutral location is preferable so that power asymmetries are not further enhanced, and a safe environment is created.

Recommendation: be mindful of equitable representation!

All participants have the right to express their opinions in a respectful way. It is important to ensure that everyone speaks the same amount of time, approximately, and that potential conflict of interests are avoided or resolved.

5.3 LL activity level

IMPLEMENTATION OF A PROJECT ACTIVITY

After all the previous preparation and planning steps, LLs should carry out each activity by incorporating all the training and information they have received.

Recommendations:

- Adopt a flexible attitude because activities in a LL do not necessarily follow a clearly defined path, and creativity comes with some degree of uncertainty.
- Encourage the interaction and sharing between the different kinds of knowledge and experience the different stakeholders embody.
- Let participants know of the rules and instructions before starting the project activity. Be clear on the participant's rights (i.e., they can withdraw their participation at any moment), and their data privacy and management.
- Ensure that everyone participates and can express their opinions in a respectful manner, in a fair distribution of time.
- Actively listen to the participants and continuously adapt the co-creation process. It can be very easy to dismiss peoples' concerns or requests, arguing that they go beyond the scope or length of the process. The fact that not everything can be included in the project does not mean that it is not worth listening to; for example, they could be included on an idea board to be considered for future projects of this LL.
- LLs often involve dialogues between science and society, where scientific experts may be reluctant to go beyond their own perspective of a particular issue. The potential strength of a LL approach is that it provides an interface for connecting expert and experiential types of knowledge. Therefore, throughout the process, it is essential to try to understand where every input comes from, to keep an open and flexible mindset, and try to sense the participants' needs.
- Do not be afraid of taking risks and possible failure, as long as the budget is not exceeded. Experimentation involves risk taking and this may lead to failure or partial success. However, even when a LL approach does not succeed in fostering innovative ideas, it can still be a source of learning in terms of process design and a source of inspiration for participants. However, if risks emerge, the WP leader must be made aware of them as early as possible.

6. COMMUNICATION – Spread the message

6.1 Project level

COMMUNICATION SUPPORT

PLAN'EAT's overall communication and dissemination strategy is presented in D6.1. Some extracts relevant to LLs are presented below:

- In PLAN'EAT, **general communication** tools and materials will be provided to inform on the project content. SPXA will implement a yearly Public Relation (PR) plan by identifying opportunities, tailoring the communication or dissemination activities (e.g., selecting which type of communication is best suited to the type of media outlet, the region and target group) and contacting, with the support of all partners, journalists (general and food related) and other communication experts working in relevant areas at national and European level.
 - Two press releases will be published per year.
 - All contents will be adapted and translated into LL languages (Swedish, Polish, French, German, English, Hungarian, Italian, Spanish and Greek).

To support LLs in media relations during the project, SPXA will also develop a PR toolkit (by M9 - May 2023) in English including:

- A roadmap summarizing the project set-up and objectives and the involved partners, and
- a Q&A document to manage press enquiries in a consistent way throughout the targeted countries.

- SPXA has designed a general social media strategy tailored to the different audience groups that will be implemented on Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram.
 - Social networks represent a way to communicate about the project and involve specific targets in PLAN'EAT activities. The LLs can use the project accounts to inform their stakeholders about project activities and results.
- SPXA will produce a guide for all partners (by M7 – March 2023) on how to properly use social networks to share content related to PLAN'EAT.

Recommendation: spread the project messages and outputs locally!

For instance, by sharing, reposting, and adapting PLAN'EAT's social media posts but also by creating new posts that target LLs specific local context, stakeholders, and target population group.

Prevent greenwashing:

No large food industry, retailer, Ilyor supermarket, even if it is a partner in local PLAN'EAT actions, may use the project for its own promotion. Each action and message inherent to the project cannot be used for commercial purposes by external organisations.

COMMUNICATION MATERIAL TO PRESENT THE PROJECT

The following material, designed by SPXA and EQY, can be used to present the project in general.

Table 3: Communication material to present the project

Material	Description
Animated infographics	
	<p>This specific content has been created to launch PLAN'EAT's social media with a very visual and easy to understand approach. The aim of these 5 videos is to get to know better:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The project, 2. Its objectives, 3. The partners, 4. The Living Labs, and 5. Their location in Europe <p>through a creative, catchy, and understandable way of communication, especially for consumers platforms such as Facebook and Instagram.</p>

Project brochure

A generic presentation to present the project, their activities and results in seminars, public hearings, meetings, conferences, and other relevant events, with the objectives to:

- inform the target audiences and engage them,
- promote the project activities and their exploitation,
- contribute to the establishment of collaborations.

COMMUNICATION CHANNEL

SPXA offers communication and social media support for the activities that are planned in each LL. A channel will be created by SPXA for Living Labs and WP leaders to:

- share documents;
- receive documents;
- answer to open surveys; and
- create specific teams and conversations.

This platform will allow communication in real time with the Living Labs and to collect the required information and their needs.

6.2 LL organisational level

DEVELOPMENT OF A LL COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

- Based on the project overall communication plan (D6.1), each LL should create its own communication strategy by defining key messages, key targets, objectives, how to achieve them and what they need from the global communication team.

- Lls should try to implement a holistic approach. Going through the activities that will be done within the project (list of practice abstracts - SPGs) can be taken as basis to build a four-year plan.

Recommendations:

- **Use a LL social media account in the local language!**

It is part of each LL’s communication strategy to decide in which way and over which platforms (e.g., LinkedIn, Facebook) they want to use social media.

Each LL can either create its own name for its LL or use the organisation's social media account. Higher reach and long-term sustainability should be considered in the decision.

- **Do not just think about a single intervention; think about a cohesive strategy!**

Communication between activities and meetings should continue on a regular basis to keep stakeholders interested and informed about what is going on in the project and the follow up of the activities they have participated into.

- The Lls can request stakeholder specific informative materials (e.g., leaflets for stakeholders, posters to recruit patients, internal newsletter etc.) from SPXA. For that, each LL should plan their needs and communicate them to SPXA in the provided communication channel.

COMMUNICATION MATERIAL TO PRESENT THE LL

Table 4: Communication material to present the LL

Tool	Description
Video interviews	
	<p>During the PLAN’EAT Kick-Off Meeting, video interviews were filmed to present the Living Labs of PLAN’EAT. This content will be disseminated little by little on the project's social networks, to meet the "faces" of the project, show all its specificities (why did they embark on the project, what are the long-term objectives...) and understand the needs of each Living Lab.</p>

Posters

Example LL HUA - Attica, exists individually for each LL

The posters aim to present each Living Lab in their specificities: where they are located, what their objectives are, which population group they are targeting. This material can be used internally and externally (in local version).

Website pages

Example LL UOC - Catalonia, exists individually for each LL

A specific page has been designed per Living Lab on [PLAN'EAT's website](#), presenting the LL target population group and specificities on the LL area. These pages will be updated throughout the project, with pictures and results from LLs, to highlight local actors and activities.

6.3 LL activity level

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE LL'S REGULAR COMMUNICATION

The LL organiser and facilitators must keep in mind that the participants are usually representatives of a much larger group, formally (such as a representative of a community organisation or NGO) or more informally (as a 'proxy' of the larger group of residents, farmers, etc.). Communication about the project and planning process, as well as formal participation processes, require careful attention so that engagement with the larger community and stakeholder groups evolves well.

Conclusions and Next steps

This toolbox (D5.1) focusses on the setting up and running of a LL and introduces tools and recommendations for the first three phases of the LL process (initiation, preparation, and co-creative design) and for communication.

The first six months were about understanding the needs of each partner that is building a LL. Individual meetings between ESSRG, EQY, and EPHA and each LL leader were organised to identify the best possible support and tools that are summarised in this toolbox.

In the next months, further support will be offered by continuing the dialogue between project and LL interests (WP5 meetings and CoP forum), and by developing further communication support (social media guide and PR toolkit).

Moreover, the tools that have not yet been used and tested by PLAN'EAT's LLs will be evaluated and, if necessary, modified and adapted.

Furthermore, a methodological framework for measuring and monitoring the impact of project instruments will be developed by M24 – August 2024.

The next deliverable on Living Labs (D5.2, M48 – August 2026) will focus on sustainability, replication, and transfer of LLs by also including the results of evaluation, feedback, testing, and a final LL experience feedback on the use of this toolbox.